

**ROLE OF AYURVEDIC THERAPIES IN EKA-KUSHTHA WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS
ON THE IMPORTANCE OF GHRITA FORMULATIONS****Dr. Ashutosh Satish Gupta*¹, Prof. Vd. Rakesh Sharma²**¹Ph.D. Scholar, Kayachikitsa Dept., Lt. SRC Ayurved College, Chikhali, Dist-Buldana, Maharashtra, India.²Ph.D. Guide, Kayachikitsa Dept., Guru Ravidas Ayurved University, Hoshiarpur, Punjab, India.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Ashutosh Satish Gupta**

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ABSTRACT

In Ayurveda, psoriasis falls under the broad category of Kushtha and because of its similar clinical characteristics; it is most closely associated with Eka-Kushtha. The main goals of Ayurvedic Kushtha management are purification of Rakta Dhatu and Shodhana, which removes vitiated Doshas, especially Vata and Kapha. Avoiding causative elements like Viruddha Ahara, eating too many salty and sour foods and experiencing psychological stress are all part of the first principle of management which is Nidana Parivarjana. The treatment approaches like Deepana-Pachana, Snehapana and Swedana can be performed before conducting therapies like Vamana, Virechana and Raktamokshana. After cleansing, exterior applications like Nimba decoction washes and medicated oils, as well as internal medications like Arogyavardhini Vati, Gandhak Rasayana and Mahamanjisthadi Kwatha are used to settle any remaining Dosha imbalance. In Ayurveda, Eka-Kushtha also managed with Ghrita (medicated ghee) since it improves dryness, itching, scaling and inflammation. It functions as a Shodhana supportive therapy and a Shamana remedy. This article explain role of Ayurvedic therapies in Eka-Kushtha with special emphasis on the importance of Ghrita formulations.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Eka-Kushtha, Skin, Ghrita, Psoriasis.**INTRODUCTION**

The majority of skin conditions are included under *Kushtha Roga* in Ayurveda, and because of their similar signs and symptoms, psoriasis can be clinically connected with *Ekakushtha*. *Ekakushtha* is the one that most closely resembles psoriasis in terms of its classical description and distinguishing characteristics. The quality of life is greatly impacted by psoriasis, a chronic inflammatory skin condition marked by erythematous plaques covered in silvery scales. It is frequently accompanied by pain, cracking, bleeding and itching, etc.^[1-3]

Ekakushtha is referred as *Vata-Kapha Pradhana Tridoshaja Vyadhi* which involves *Dushyas* such *Lasika, Rasa, Rakta* and *Mamsa*. Traditional signs and symptoms include *Aswedanam, Matsyashakalopamam, Krishna-Aruna Varnata* and *Mahavastu. Vegadharana, Divaswapna*, excessive consumption of *Guru, Snigdha, Drava Ahara* and *Navanna* as well as psychological or

immoral activities are among the etiological elements. *Vata* and *Kapha Doshas*, circulate through *Tiryakvahini Siras* and localize in the *Bahya Rogamarga*. *Twacha, Rakta, Mamsa* and *Lasika* are mostly vitiated by these variables, resulting in distinctive lesions.^[4-6]

The primary method of treating vitiated *Doshas* in *Kushtha* is *Shodhana Chikitsa*. *Virechana* is particularly recommended among *Panchakarma* techniques since it effectively balances *Vata* and *Kapha* while also getting rid of *Pitta* and *Rakta Dushti*. Compared to *Vamana*, it is thought to be less stressful and somewhat safer. The primary therapeutic approach consists of repeated *Samshodhana* along with *Samshamana* therapy. *Bahya Parimarjana* and *Antah Parimarjana* are advises for complete relief from disease. As demonstrated by long-lasting remission at follow-up, Ayurvedic treatment of psoriasis with *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapies provides a methodical, comprehensive, and long-lasting approach, addressing the underlying *Dosha* imbalance and

lowering recurrence. The major pathological events of *Ekakushtha* are depicted in **Figure 1**.^[5-7]

Figure 1: Pathological events associated with *Ekakushtha*.

The major causative factors of disease includes *Viruddha Aahara*, excessive intake of *Guru*, *Snigdha*, *Drava* and *Navanna*, etc. Other factors are genetic predisposition,

local trauma, infections and adverse effects of modern day life style. The key elements associated in *Samprapti* of disease are mentioned in **Table 1**.^[6-8]

Table 1: Pathological Events Associated With *Ekakushtha*.

S. No.	Pathological Factors	Descriptions
1	<i>Tridosha</i> Vitiating	Primarily <i>Vata</i> and <i>Kapha</i>
2	<i>Dhatu</i>	<i>Twacha</i> , <i>Rakta</i> and <i>Mamsa</i>
3	<i>Srota</i>	Blockage in <i>Swedavaha Srotas</i>
4	<i>Agni</i>	<i>Mandagni</i>

Management

A comprehensive strategy that incorporates *Shodhana*, *Shamana*, and rigorous devotion to *Pathya-Apathya* is the foundation for *Kayachikitsa's* management of *Ekakushtha*, which is clinically connected with psoriasis. Restoring good skin, purifying *Rakta Dhatu*, balancing the *Vata* and *Kapha Doshas*, and detoxifying the body are the main goals. Depending on the patient's condition, several *Shodhana* therapies are used, such as *Vamana* to remove aggravated *Kapha*, *Virechana* to purify blood and expel vitiated *Pitta*, *Basti* to cure *Vata* imbalance, and *Raktamokshana* to treat *Rakta Dushti*. In addition to purification, *Shamana* therapy with herbal medicines like as *Khadira*, *Neem*, *Haridra*, *Manjistha*, *Guggulu* and *Kumari* helps in blood purification, inflammation reduction and skin healing.^[7-9]

Traditional formulas that promote detoxification and *Dosha* balancing include *Arogyavardhini Vati*, *Panchatikta Ghrita* and *Mahamanjishtadi Kwatha*. External treatments for scaling, irritation, dryness and redness include *Thakradhara*, *Taila*, *Lepa* and *Takra* applications. In order to establish long-term remission and avoid recurrence, Ayurvedic management places a strong emphasis on systemic purification in addition to internal and exterior therapies. In Ayurveda, *Eka-Kushtha* also managed with *Ghrita* since it improves itching, scaling and dryness, etc.

Therapeutic Importance of Role of *Ghrita*

Some bitter herbs such as; *Nimba*, *Patola*, *Vyaghri*, *Guduchi* and *Vasa* are used to make *Ghrita* formulation.

It has historically been used to treat inflammatory diseases, chronic ulcers, and a variety of skin ailments. Its *Tridosha-shamaka* qualities, especially its effects on *Pitta* and *Kapha* helps in the purification of *Rakta*. *Ghrita* reduces inflammation and encourages healthy skin. *Ghrita* also applied to the lesions for local healing and systemic detoxification.

According to contemporary science, psoriasis is a T-cell-mediated autoimmune disease that is characterized by chronic activation of T-lymphocytes, which causes rapid epidermal turnover and plaque formation. This is the likely mechanism of action of *Ghrita*. According to reports, *Khadira* contains immune-modulatory and antioxidant qualities that may help control cytotoxic T-cell activity and lessen inflammatory reactions, which in turn may help to reduce the thickness of lesions. The skin is particularly vulnerable to oxidative damage brought on by reactive oxygen species because it is continuously exposed to UV light and environmental stress. Psoriasis advances as a result of decreased antioxidant defense and increased oxidative stress. According to studies, phenolic compounds found in formulation offer strong antioxidant and free radical-scavenging properties, which may shield epidermal tissue from oxidative damage.^[6-8]

Effective drug transport to the cellular level is crucial for the best possible therapeutic impact in Ayurveda. Because of its *Yogavahi* feature, which increases the bioavailability and penetration of active ingredients, *Ghrita* is considered as *Sneha*. The *ghee* basis promotes better pharmacological effect and deeper tissue

absorption since cell membranes easily allow lipid-soluble compounds. Thus, by combining immunomodulatory, antioxidant, and improved delivery benefits.

The medicinal use of *Ghrita* in treating *Ekakushtha* is important due to its unctuous quality. This quality helps to treat skin dryness, scaling, and irritation. *Ghrita* also calms excess *Vata* and *Pitta doshas*, thus relieving burning sensation, inflammation, redness, and pain caused by psoriasis lesions. Additionally, it has a *Kushtaghna* property and *Kandughna* property. As a *Raktashodhaka*, *Ghrita* helps to purify the blood, which is vital for treating chronic dermatological conditions. The *Varnya* property helps to improve the texture and tone of the skin. The *Shothahara* property helps to decrease inflammation and the thickening of plaque.

From a physiological perspective, *Ghrita* is a *Yogavahi* for delivering herbal constituents to deeper levels of the *Dhatu*s and improves their ability to do so. Additionally, *Ghrita* helps in *Srotoshodhana* and liquefying vitiated *Doshas* for their easy elimination. The lipophilic disposition of *Ghrita* also allows for easy absorption through cellular membranes, thus providing nourishment and repair to the skin tissues.^[8-10]

CONCLUSION

Based on similarities in clinical presentation, etiology, and chronic recurrent nature, psoriasis and *Ekakushtha*, which are both mentioned under *Kushtha Roga* in Ayurveda, can be effectively connected. The management of this *Vata-Kapha* dominant *Tridoshaja Vyadhi*, which involves *Rasa*, *Rakta*, *Mamsa*, and *Lasika*, necessitates a thorough and cause-based approach. With the help of repeated *Samshodhana* and *Samshamana* therapies, Ayurvedic treatment places a strong emphasis on *Shodhana Chikitsa* as the primary method of removing vitiated *Doshas*, especially through procedures like *Virechana*. Together, internal drugs, exterior treatments, and rigorous adherence to *Pathya-Apathya* helps in purifying *Rakta Dhatu*, restoring *Dosha* equilibrium and averting recurrence. Because of their *Tridosha-shamaka*, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and *Yogavahi* qualities, medicated *Ghrita* preparations improve therapeutic results. These formulations help in lesion reduction and long-lasting remission by promoting deeper tissue penetration and modifying oxidative and immunological systems.

REFERENCES

1. Vd. Jadavji T. Acharya, Charaka Samhita (with Ayurveda-Dipika Commentary by Chakrapanidatta), Nidana Sthana, Chapter 5/4, Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashana, Varanasi, 2005; 216.
2. Vipul Kanani et. al, Manasika Bhavas in Eka Kushta (Psoriasis), dept. of Kayachikitsa, IPGTandRA, GAU, Jamnagar 6. Ibidem (3), Cha. Chikitsa Sthana, 2002; 7/39: 329.

3. M Ashvini Kumar et al. Int. J. Res. Ayurveda Pharm. 4(4), Jul– Aug, Critical Appraisal of Virechana Karma In Psoriasis, 2013; 595-598.
4. Chandrasekar R, Sivagami B. Alternative treatment for psoriasis: A review, IJRDP, 2016; 5(4): 2188-2197.
5. Bulusu S, editor, Bhavaprakash of Bhavmishra, chapter 54, Verse 8: Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi, 2010; 529.
6. Sharma PV, editor, Susruta Samhita, Nidana Sthana, Chapter 5, Verse 9, Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy, Varanasi, 2010; 824.
7. Shukla V, Tripathi RV, editors, Charak Samhita, Chikitsa sthana, Chaptar 7, verse 139, Chukhamba Sanskrit pratishthan, Delhi, 2010; 186.
8. Shukla V, Tripathi RV, editors, Charak Samhita, Chikitsa sthana, chaptar 7, verse 159, Chukhamba Sanskrit pratishthan, Delhi, 2010; 200.
9. Wagner, Hikino. Economic and Medicinal Plant Research. Vol. II, New York: Academic Press, 1992; 53.
10. Swanbeck G, Inerot A, Martinsson T, Wahlström J. A population genetic study of psoriasis. Br J Dermatol, 1994; 131: 32-9.